

Bolstering Entrepreneurship Intention Through Project Biz-VISION among Business and Management Tertiary Students: A Multi-Path Structural Equation Modeling Analysis

Desiree Rose S. Nistal ,
Ariane Jane Garces

School of Business and Management Education, Student, Holy Cross of Davao College, Davao City, Philippines

Abstract

Entrepreneurial intention among students in developing countries remains a pressing concern due to varying levels of business knowledge and external influences. This study aimed to evaluate whether attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control significantly mediate the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention among business administration students of Holy Cross of Davao College, using the Extended Theory of Planned Behavior. The study employed a quantitative nonexperimental design with a predictive correlational approach, surveying 293 business and management students selected through convenience sampling. Data analysis utilized mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and Structural Equation Modeling with multiple path analysis. Results consistently showed that students demonstrated a very high level of business knowledge, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention, with significant correlations observed among these variables. Furthermore, attitude and perceived behavioral control jointly mediated the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention, while subjective norms did not. To further enhance students' entrepreneurial intention, the study strongly recommends implementing Project Biz-VISION. The findings contribute to the existing body of knowledge on entrepreneurial intention in higher education, providing insights for higher education policymakers, business and management educators and students, and future researchers on fostering entrepreneurship among students in developing economies.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial intention, business knowledge, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, Extended Theory of Planned Behavior, structural equation modeling, higher education, business and management students, Holy Cross of Davao College, Project Biz-VISION.*

JEL Classification codes: *M10, M12, L20, L26*

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Introduction

Entrepreneurial intention among students encounters problems globally, such as in Spain, wherein they are lagging behind in the ranking of countries regarding the entrepreneurial intention of their university students (Barba-Sánchez et al., 2022). In China, for example, many undergraduates are not able to follow their will, and the possibility of realizing their entrepreneurial intention is relatively low (Lihua, 2022). Female university students in Saudi Arabia showed low entrepreneurial intentions (Alshagawi, 2019, as cited by Al-Mamary et al., 2020). Alarmingly, only seventeen percent (17%) of the graduate students in Indonesia want to pursue an entrepreneurial career since it is not considered an important career in the country (Sahban, 2016). Despite being one of the most chosen college programs, entrepreneurship encounters a high drop-out rate due to loss of interest or students making a wrong decision regarding their career path (Depoo & Hajerová-Mullerová, 2024).

In the Philippines, students pursuing an entrepreneurship program encounter significant obstacles that negatively affect their entrepreneurial intentions (Romero & Gono, 2021). Business students from three selected universities in Pampanga assessed themselves as having low entrepreneurial capabilities and skills (Valencia et al., 2022). In Liceo De Los Baños, unexpectedly, senior high school students pursuing the General Academic strand showed high entrepreneurial intention compared to students pursuing the Accountancy, Business, and Management strand, which had lower entrepreneurial intention (Mendoza, 2024). Aside from the low business self-efficacy that was recorded, college students who graduated in the year 2015 at the University of the Philippines Los Baños show a low level of entrepreneurial intention (Medina, 2022). Filipino students exhibit a lack of interest in entrepreneurship regardless of the government initiatives aiming to promote the program (Belmonte et al., 2022).

In a study conducted at Davao Del Sur State College, it has been reviewed in the literature that there is little understanding of the factors that affect students' intentions of becoming entrepreneurs (Demillo & Demillo, 2022). Entrepreneurial behavior and even commitment have been seen as far from actual practice, which is evident in the study of the University of Mindanao, where only 31% (11 out of 35) of the entrepreneurship program graduates have pursued entrepreneurial careers (Romero et al., 2021). There is no scholarly intention given in conducting an investigation into students' initial plans to participate and enroll in business programs, especially in the Davao Region (Cain & Sucuhai, 2024).

Research on college students' entrepreneurial intention has largely focused on entrepreneurship education and intention, with limited exploration of other influencing factors (Mukhtar et al., 2021). While studies have examined self-efficacy and the post-pandemic entrepreneurial environment, other potential determinants of entrepreneurial intention remain underexplored (Zhang & Huang, 2021). Additionally, most scholarly investigations on college students' entrepreneurial intentions have been conducted in East Asia (Bu et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2023), with limited emphasis on Southeast Asia. The lack of empirical research on entrepreneurial intention in emerging economies further highlights a critical gap (Sampene et al., 2023), and the Philippines is no exception.

With the reviewed literature and studies, this study addresses these gaps by extending the Theory of Planned Behavior through the inclusion of business knowledge as an additional factor influencing entrepreneurial intention. The researchers firmly believed that this study contributes to the existing body of knowledge, which is predominantly based on research from developed regions since this study is primarily focused on college students from a developing country enrolled in a Catholic higher education institution.

Statement of the Problem

This study examined how business knowledge influences entrepreneurial intention among students pursuing business administration programs at Holy Cross of Davao College. It also explored whether attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control mediate this relationship. The study aimed to provide insights into how business education shapes students' motivation to pursue entrepreneurship. Hence, below are the research objectives of the study:

1. To determine the level of business knowledge in terms of business management, legal, and strategic knowledge, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention among students of Holy Cross of Davao College pursuing business administration programs.
2. To examine whether there is a significant correlation among business knowledge, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention among students of Holy Cross of Davao College pursuing business administration programs.
3. To evaluate whether attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control significantly mediate the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention among students of Holy Cross of Davao College pursuing business administration programs.
4. To devise a learning and development program to boost the entrepreneurial intention among students of Holy Cross of Davao College pursuing business administration programs based on the inferential results of the study.

Theoretical Framework

This study is theoretically grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Icek Ajzen (1991), which Yang and Choi (2022) extended by incorporating knowledge as a factor influencing behavioral intention. Initially, TPB posits that attitude toward the behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control affect an individual's intention to engage in a specific behavior (Ara, 2003). However, recent findings suggest that knowledge also plays a significant role in shaping behavioral intention, justifying its inclusion as an additional predictor. In this study, business knowledge serves as the independent variable, while attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control act as mediators in influencing entrepreneurial intention among business administration students at Holy Cross of Davao College. The Extended TPB is relevant to this study because it provides an extended framework for understanding how knowledge and psychological factors collectively shape students' entrepreneurial aspirations.

Materials and Methods

Research Design. The study is grounded in post-positivist worldview which utilizes a quantitative nonexperimental design employing a predictive-correlational approach. The correlational research design is suitable for this investigation due to the use of multiple quantitative variables in the prediction of a relationship (Gall et al., 2007, as cited by Riddle, 2018). This nonexperimental approach was selected to determine if a predictive relationship exists among knowledge, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention (Çolak, 2023). More than the relationship, the study aimed to further investigate whether attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control mediate the relationship between knowledge and entrepreneurial intention among students pursuing business administration programs at Holy Cross of Davao College. With this, the chosen research design and approach are appropriate to answer the study's research objective.

Locale of the Study. The study is conducted in the Holy Cross of Davao College—a private Catholic higher education institution recognized by the Commission of Higher Education. The locale is appropriate for this study as the school offers a business program with three majors: marketing management, financial management, and human resource management. The researchers chose to examine this topic from the perspective of higher education, as both higher education and entrepreneurial activities are key drivers of economic growth, job creation, entrepreneurship, and poverty alleviation (Wang et al., 2011, as cited by Deng & Wang, 2023). Formal education plays a crucial role in influencing students' entrepreneurial choices and success; however, a gap between education and entrepreneurial demands presents a significant challenge (Kang & Xiong, 2021; Wright et al., 2022).

Moreover, entrepreneurship education is closely linked to promoting entrepreneurship and can effectively address the discrepancies between the education provided by formal higher education institutions and the needs of entrepreneurs, enhancing both entrepreneurial intentions and success rates among prospective business professionals (Aly et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2021; Wright et al., 2022). Some researchers argue that entrepreneurial education in public universities has a more positive impact on students' entrepreneurial intentions than that in private universities (Wang et al., 2023), while other studies present contrasting findings (Bergmann et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2014).

Sample and Sampling Technique. Out of 1,261 enrolled students who are pursuing business administration programs with specializations in marketing management, financial management, and human resource management, this study involved 293 students out of 295 required sample size as calculated by Raosoft online sample size calculator following a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and 50% population proportion. The researchers administered a total of 295 printed survey questionnaires; upon return, the researchers were able to validate that out of 295 returned survey questionnaires, only 293 of them were filled out. Hence, there is a 99.66% survey turnout.

Moreover, the students who are pursuing business administration programs were selected using a convenience sampling technique. Convenience sampling is the selection of study subjects because they conform to stipulated standards like easy accessibility, proximity in the geographical area, availability at a given time, and the willingness to partake in given research (Pabst et al., 2021; Stratton, 2023). A predictive-correlational study also employed the convenience sampling technique due to its affordability, ease, and readily availability of the subjects (Mensah et al., 2021). Lastly, the inclusion-exclusion criteria that were implemented in this study are as follows: male, female, or members of the LGBTQ+, 18 years old and above, pursuing business administration programs with specializations in marketing management, financial management, and human resource management, enrolled in Holy Cross of Davao College for the academic school year 2023-2024, and willing to provide voluntary consent to be part of the study.

Research Instrument. An adapted structured survey questionnaire was utilized in this study. There is a need to modify some indicators for it to be relevant in the study's context (Abendaño, 2025). To gauge business knowledge, the researchers utilized the Basic Business Knowledge Scale developed by Bernal-Guerrero et al. (2020). The 20-item adapted multidimensional scale contains three (3) domains, which are business management knowledge, legal knowledge, and strategic knowledge. On the other hand, personal attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention were assessed using Liñán and Chen's (2009) Personal Attitude (5 items), Subjective Norm (3 items), Perceived Behavioral Control (6 items), and Entrepreneurial Intention (6 items) multidimensional scales. The students who are pursuing business administration programs were able to provide their responses using a 4-point Likert scale where 4 stands for strongly agree, 3 for agree, 2 for disagree, and 1 for strongly disagree.

Moreover, the adapted survey questionnaire was validated by three experts in the field of business and management research. The evaluators assessed the survey questionnaire in the following aspects: clarity of directions and items, presentation of items, suitability of items, adequateness, attainment of purpose, and objectivity. The result of the validation of the survey questionnaire obtained a general average of 3.72 or satisfactory. The questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing wherein 15 business administration students from the 3 programs were involved. Overall, the adapted survey questionnaire obtained a Cronbach's alpha of 0.92, wherein items demonstrated excellent internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedure. The researchers secured an endorsement and permission to conduct the study immediately after successfully defending it before the panel of examiners. The Vice President for Academic Affairs signed and recognized the endorsement letter. Following this, the researchers administered and collected informed consent forms from business administration students through face-to-face interaction. Only students who provided signed informed consent were deemed eligible to participate in the survey phase, which was also conducted and collected in person. After gathering the survey responses, the researchers tabulated the data and submitted the summarized survey results to a chosen statistician for analysis. Upon receiving the analyzed data, the researchers moved with interpretation, discussion, conclusion, and recommendations. Finally, to ensure data confidentiality and ethical adherence, the researchers disposed of all research-related documents by shredding hard copies and deleting soft copies from the lead researcher's Google Drive.

Data Analysis. Descriptive statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation were used to answer research objective one of the study. Moreover, inferential statistical tools, particularly Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, were used to answer research objective two, and structural equation modeling through mediation analysis was employed to answer research objective three. Hypotheses testing was done based on α 0.05 level of significance. Data visualization was done through tabular and model presentations.

Ethical Considerations. Under the Department of Science and Technology and Philippine Health Research Ethics Board mandate and aligned with the institutional Holy Cross of Davao College Research Ethics Committee's nine elements, these ethical protocols ensured that research endeavors prioritize the dignity and welfare of individuals involved in this study. Researchers acknowledged their moral responsibility to protect the respondents of this study, which are the business and administration students, from potential harm, uphold informed consent, maintain confidentiality, and ensure transparency before, during, and after the conduct of this study. The nine elements are social value, informed consent, risk, benefits and safety, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the researcher, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement. The researchers obtained approval from the Holy Cross of Davao College-Research Ethics Committee on December 4, 2023, and they received the certification through Google electronic mail on December 7, 2023.

Results

Level of Knowledge, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students of the Holy Cross of Davao College

The statistical findings indicate that the 293 business administration students of Holy Cross of Davao College demonstrated a very high level of business knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.39$, $SD = 0.42$). Within this factor, students exhibited very high knowledge in business management ($\bar{x} = 3.34$, $SD = 0.47$), legal knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.33$, $SD = 0.51$), and strategic knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.50$, $SD = 0.45$). Their attitude towards entrepreneurship also reached a very high level ($\bar{x} = 3.51$, $SD = 0.50$) alongside

their subjective norm ($\bar{x} = 3.45$, $SD = 0.54$). Meanwhile, their perceived behavioral control was rated high ($\bar{x} = 3.08$, $SD = 0.67$). Lastly, their entrepreneurial intention is also very high ($\bar{x} = 3.39$, $SD = 0.61$), suggesting strong entrepreneurial motivation among the business administration students of Holy Cross of Davao College.

Table 1. Level of Knowledge, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students of the Holy Cross of Davao College (N=293)

Variable	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
1. Business Knowledge	3.39	0.42	Very High
1.1. Knowledge in Business Management	3.34	0.47	Very High
1.2. Legal Knowledge	3.33	0.51	Very High
1.3. Strategic Knowledge	3.50	0.45	Very High
2. Attitude	3.51	0.50	Very High
3. Subjective Norm	3.45	0.54	Very High
4. Perceived Behavioral Control	3.08	0.67	High
5. Entrepreneurial Intention	3.39	0.61	Very High

Note: 3.26 – 4.00 is Very High, 2.51-3.25 is High, 1.76 – 2.50 is Low, and 1.00 – 1.75 is Very Low

Bivariate Correlations Among Knowledge, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students of the Holy Cross of Davao College

The bivariate correlation analysis reveals that knowledge demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with attitude ($r = 0.544$, $p < 0.001$), subjective norm ($r = 0.485$, $p < 0.001$), perceived behavioral control ($r = 0.617$, $p < 0.001$), and entrepreneurial intention ($r = 0.514$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher knowledge levels among students were associated with more positive attitudes, stronger subjective norms, greater perceived control, and higher entrepreneurial intention. Moreover, attitude exhibited a strong positive correlation with entrepreneurial intention ($r = 0.706$, $p < 0.001$) and a moderate correlation with subjective norm ($r = 0.548$, $p < 0.001$) and perceived behavioral control ($r = 0.582$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that students with a more favorable attitude toward entrepreneurship were more likely to intend to pursue entrepreneurship-related ventures.

Table 2. Bivariate Correlations Among Knowledge, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students of the Holy Cross of Davao College

Variable	1	2	3	4	5
1. Knowledge	-	-	-	-	-
2. Attitude	0.544***	-	-	-	-
3. Subjective Norm	0.485***	0.548***	-	-	-
4. Perceived Behavioral Control	0.617***	0.582***	0.506***	-	-
5. Entrepreneurial Intention	0.514***	0.706***	0.494***	0.639***	-

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Looking into another factor, subjective norm showed a moderate correlation with perceived behavioral control ($r = 0.506$, $p < 0.001$) and entrepreneurial intention ($r = 0.494$, $p < 0.001$), signifying those social influences played a role in shaping students' perceived control over

entrepreneurial tasks and their intention to engage in entrepreneurship. Perceived behavioral control demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with entrepreneurial intention ($r = 0.639, p < 0.001$), indicating that students who felt more capable of performing entrepreneurial activities were more likely to express intentions to become entrepreneurs. Collectively, with the significant positive correlations recorded, the following null hypotheses were rejected: $H_01, H_02, H_03, H_04, H_05, H_06, H_07, H_08, H_09$, and H_010 .

Path Analysis of Knowledge, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students of the Holy Cross of Davao College

The third objective of this study is to conduct a path examination of knowledge, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention among business administration students at the Holy Cross of Davao College. The study sought to uncover the patterns of influences among these variables that are based on the extended theory of planned behavior, providing comprehensive insights into the factors that truly drive entrepreneurial intentions within business administration students enrolled in a Catholic higher education institution. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 3, highlighting the connections and implications for future entrepreneurial pursuits among the students.

Table 3. Path Analysis of Knowledge, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students of the Holy Cross of Davao College

Effect	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper
A. Direct						
Knowledge → Entrepreneurial Intention	0.086	0.121	0.709	0.478	-0.239	0.395
B. Indirect Effect						
Knowledge → Attitude	0.611	0.086	7.104	< 0.001	0.429	0.836
Knowledge → Subjective Norm	0.068	0.055	1.236	0.216	-0.058	0.223
Knowledge → Perceived Behavioral Control	0.456	.084	5.407	< 0.001	0.265	0.686
C. Total Effects						
Knowledge → Entrepreneurial Intention	<1.221	0.119	10.265	< 0.001	0.923	1.515
D. Total Indirect Effects						
Knowledge → Entrepreneurial Intention	1.135	0.112	10.096	< 0.001	0.870	1.409
E. Residual Covariances						
Attitude ↔ Subjective Norm	0.283	0.046	6.182	< 0.001	0.182	0.410
Attitude ↔ Perceived Behavioral Control	0.245	0.041	5.973	< 0.001	0.153	0.352
Subjective Norm ↔ Perceived Behavioral Control	0.206	0.042	4.933	< 0.001	0.094	0.350

Note: Number of bootstrap samples for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals: 5,000 and R2: Entrepreneurial Intention = 0.581; Attitude = 0.296; Subjective Norm = 0.235; and Perceived Behavioral Control = 0.381

The path analysis results indicate that knowledge does not exhibit a significant direct effect on entrepreneurial intention ($\beta = 0.086, p = 0.478$), suggesting that knowledge alone does not directly predict entrepreneurial intention among business administration students enrolled in Holy Cross of Davao College. However, the indirect effect analysis reveals that knowledge significantly influences entrepreneurial intention through attitude ($\beta = 0.611, p < 0.001$) and perceived behavioral control ($\beta = 0.456, p < 0.001$). In contrast, its indirect effect through subjective norm is not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.068, p = 0.216$). This means that the decision for H_012 is to fail

to be rejected. The total effect of knowledge on entrepreneurial intention is significant ($\beta = 1.221$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the combined direct and indirect effects contribute to entrepreneurial intention. The total indirect effect is also significant ($\beta = 1.135$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that attitude and perceived behavioral control serve as strong mediators, which means that H_{011} and H_{013} are rejected.

Moreover, the residual covariances indicate significant relationships among the mediating variables, with attitude correlating with subjective norm ($\beta = 0.283$, $p < 0.001$) and perceived behavioral control ($\beta = 0.245$, $p < 0.001$), while subjective norm also correlates with perceived behavioral control ($\beta = 0.206$, $p < 0.001$). These observed significant relationships indicate interconnected influences among these psychological factors. The R-squared values illustrate that the model explains 58.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial intention, which means that there is a strong predictive power manifested. Attitude accounts for 29.6% of its variance, subjective norm accounts for 23.5%, and perceived behavioral control explains 38.1%, highlighting the varying degrees to which these factors contribute to entrepreneurial intention among business administration students of the Holy Cross of Davao College.

Figure 1. Structural Path Model Analyzing the Effects of Attitude, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioral Control on the Relationship Between Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Intention Among Business Administration Students in the Holy Cross of Davao College

Cross Blazers’ Biz-VISION: Devised Program Intended for Business Administration Students Enrolled in the Holy Cross of Davao College

The Cross Blazers' Biz-VISION program aims to produce business administration graduates who are not just confident but also innovative and competent to launch and sustain their business ventures in the near future, as they will be equipped with relevant business skills. The program is set to enhance their entrepreneurial mindset, strengthen their risk-taking ability, and expected to improve their business competence through hands-on learning and mentorship. As a result, the business administration graduates of the Holy Cross of Davao College will not only pursue entrepreneurship but also have the potency to contribute to economic growth by creating jobs, introducing market innovations, and fostering a culture of business leadership. Ultimately, the

program seeks to increase the number of HCDC graduates who actively engage in entrepreneurship, reducing the gap between business education and entrepreneurial action. Shown in Figure 3 is the visionary aim of the developed program.

Discussion

The business administration students of Holy Cross of Davao College showed a high level of strategic knowledge. Their profound knowledge of these key strategic concepts confirms they excel in identifying and understanding business opportunities, which aligns with the study of Nongsuwan (2017); students who exhibit this level of competence are assertive, proactive problem-solvers who put significant emphasis on quality, continuous learning, and growth. Also, students show a high level of knowledge in business management and exhibit a solid grasp of stakeholder roles, benchmarking techniques, SWOT analysis, corporate social responsibility, ethical business codes, financial processes, accounting principles, economic-financial planning, product and service characteristics, and logo creation.

In relation to the results, it was found out that it is consistent with the study of Shmeleva (2020), who pointed out that students not only exhibit a high level of knowledge in business management but also effectively employ this knowledge to address actual real-world business challenges. Furthermore, the legal knowledge of business administration students is also rated as very high. This shows that there is strong evidence of a strong grasp of understanding fundamental legal concepts required for business operations, such as minimum capital requirements, partner responsibilities, organizational structures, firm types, and business start-up procedures. This finding is consistent with the study of Avendaño et al. (2022), which showed that students have a strong legal foundation and a positive learning in subjects with legal or juridical topics.

The study found that business administration students of the Holy Cross of Davao College obtain a high level of attitude towards entrepreneurship, which aligns with the study of Cano et al. (2022), who found that students possess a high entrepreneurial attitude, showing a strong inclination to pursue it as a career and expressed a desire to establish a business if given the opportunity and resources because of its perceived advantages and job appeal. Additionally, business administration students also exhibit a high level of subjective norm, meaning that their friends, family, and peers support and encourage them in their entrepreneurial endeavors; consistent with Al-Ghani et al. (2022), students who display a high level of subjective norm are more likely have ambition to start their venture with the support from peers and parents.

Business administration students demonstrated a high level of perceived behavioral control and showed a strong inclination toward entrepreneurial, evidenced by their willingness to take the necessary measures to start and operate their own business, which aligns with the study by Wahyuni and Partrini (2021) reveals that students have a high level of perceived behavioral control are more likely to exhibit entrepreneurial intention, indicate a strong desire to launch a business. In addition, business administration students show a high level of entrepreneurial intention, demonstrating readiness for management during the start-up phase with their expertise in understanding needed to create, start, and keep a positive outlook in entrepreneurial endeavors, similar to the study of Saraih et al. (2018), where students display a high level of entrepreneurial intention, which supports their strong entrepreneurial attitude and preparation for next business endeavors.

Business knowledge possesses a significant correlation with entrepreneurial intention (Liao et al., 2022), and this reveals that when students possess higher knowledge levels, the same goes for their entrepreneurial intent. Business knowledge also exhibits a significant correlation with attitude (Hussain et al., 2021), suggesting that students with business knowledge develop a positive outlook toward entrepreneurship. A significant correlation exists between business knowledge and

subjective norms (Aga & Singh, 2022), which only shows that societal and peer influences are stronger among those with higher business knowledge. Business knowledge also significantly correlates with perceived behavioral control (Muliadi et al., 2021), meaning that students with more knowledge feel more capable of starting a business.

Moreover, the attitude has a significant correlation with entrepreneurial intention (Ambad & Damit, 2016); with this result, students with a positive attitude increase the likelihood of pursuing entrepreneurship. Subjective norm significantly correlates with entrepreneurial intention (Maydiantoro et al., 2021), showing that social expectations influence entrepreneurial choices. Perceived behavioral control has a significant correlation with entrepreneurial intention (Vamvaka et al., 2020), suggesting that students who believe in their capability and are capable of really executing it, like starting a business, are more likely to act. Attitude significantly correlates with subjective norms (Dince & Budic, 2016), showing that personal views align with social expectations. Attitude and perceived behavioral control are also correlated significantly (Wijayati et al., 2021), meaning that a positive attitude intensifies confidence in entrepreneurial capabilities. Lastly, subjective norm significantly correlates with perceived behavioral control (Majeed et al., 2021), revealing that social influences truly can shape entrepreneurial action confidence.

The findings indicate that attitude and perceived behavioral control serve as significant mediators in the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention (Wibowo, Abdinagoro, & Purwana, 2022), highlighting their crucial role in shaping students' entrepreneurial aspirations. Specifically, students with higher business knowledge tend to develop more positive attitudes and a stronger sense of control over entrepreneurial activities, which, in turn, enhances their intention to pursue entrepreneurship. Conversely, while subjective norms influence this relationship, they do not act as mediators between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention. This aligns with the study of Pham (2023), which found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy and attitude fully mediated the relationship, whereas subjective norms were negatively moderated by entrepreneurial education. Additionally, the findings indicate that although entrepreneurship education did not have a direct effect on entrepreneurial intention, it contributed to an increase in entrepreneurial intention through attitude toward entrepreneurship and perceived behavioral control (Duong, 2021; Wibowo, Abdinagoro, & Purwana, 2022). These findings emphasize the importance of fostering a supportive educational environment that enhances students' confidence and positive outlook toward entrepreneurship, ultimately facilitating their transition from theoretical knowledge to entrepreneurial action.

Attitude and perceived behavioral control fully mediated the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention among college students taking up business administration programs. This is supported by Duong's study (2021). However, subjective norms did not mediate the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention. Furthermore, the researchers created a one-year learning and development program to strengthen the entrepreneurial intention of business administration students. Entrepreneurship education increases students' confidence and willingness to start a business (Ahmed et al., 2020). To prepare them better, educators must provide enough training before graduation so students feel ready to take risks and start their ventures (Udekwe & Iwu, 2024). Practical learning is also essential—students need real-world experience, not just theories. Schools should offer hands-on activities and access to tools and technology to help students develop the skills they need to succeed in business (Okeke, 2024).

The findings partially affirm the Extended Theory of Planned Behavior by reinforcing the significance of subjective norms in shaping students' entrepreneurial intention when examined independently. However, when analyzed alongside attitude and perceived behavioral control, the subjective norm does not mediate the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention, suggesting that social influence alone may not directly drive students

toward entrepreneurship when other cognitive and behavioral factors are considered. As per a further examination, the researchers believed that, based on the inferential findings of the study, it challenges the assumption that subjective norms universally strengthen entrepreneurial intention and instead highlights the dominant roles of attitude and perceived behavioral control in this process. Thus, while the extended theory remains relevant, the findings suggest a need to reconsider the mediating role of subjective norms within the entrepreneurial context.

Conclusion

Consistently, business administration students of the Holy Cross of Davao College demonstrated very high levels of business knowledge, attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurial intention. Moreover, all these variables exhibited a significant positive correlation. Although subjective norm alone is an influential factor in entrepreneurial intention, only attitude and perceived behavioral control fully mediate the relationship between business knowledge and entrepreneurial intention. The expanded theory of planned behavior is supported by the findings derived from this study. Lastly, to bolster business administration students' entrepreneurial intention, Project Biz-VISION was devised based on the inferential findings of the study.

Researchers must continue conducting research that addresses the pressing needs of the society (Cayas et al., 2024). With this, future researchers should explore the 41.9% of uncharted factors that may influence students' entrepreneurial intention, as through this, a scientific understanding of the determinants of entrepreneurial intention will be established. Conducting a longitudinal study or employing a mixed-method approach would provide deeper insights and further substantiate the findings. It is highly recommended to conduct further studies pertaining to entrepreneurial intention among Filipino students. Moreover, educational administrators and business administration faculty must go beyond enhancing students' business knowledge by also strengthening their attitudes and perceived behavioral control toward entrepreneurship, as these factors are crucial in solidifying their entrepreneurial intention—a prerequisite for entrepreneurial behavior. Additionally, implementing Project Biz-VISION could serve as a strategic initiative to support and develop students' entrepreneurial competencies which may also contribute to the achievement of the following United Nation Sustainable Development Goals: quality education (SDG 4), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), industry, innovation, and infrastructure (SDG 9), and partnership for the goals (SDG 17).

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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